

Advion expression CMS

This guideline explains the integration process of an Advion expression CMS controlled via Advion Mass Express ver.4.0.13.8 in Windows 10 into the Chemotion ELN. The procedure is split into three aspects that can be set up independently or in parallel:

1. Remote connection to the device
2. Post-processing conversion of files into open formats
3. transfer of experiment data to the ELN.

Considering all the [general preparation aspects](#), this procedure has been conducted on the following system configurations. However, it is likely to work on systems with different software versions as well.

Specifications of the device's PC

- Operating system: Windows 10
- Software Name: Advion Mass Express ver.4.0.13.8
- Connected to LAN (Intranet only): Yes
- Data files generated: *.datx
- Automatic conversion to: netCDF
- Static IP address has been configured

Objectives

- Remote Device Control
- Data transfer to Chemotion ELN inbox

Configurations

Remote Device Control

General guidelines regarding the configurations of remote device control can be found [here](#).

Data transfer

Data will automatically be transferred to the Chemotion ELN once LabSolutions has finished recording data of the current run. The user is required to input a valid file output name according to the [naming convention](#) for the Chemotion ELN to sort the file into the correct user's inbox.

Data Conversion

Necessary configuration in LabSolutions

In the Advion Mass Express "Auto Run" window enter the "Auto Run Setup" tab and activate the "Exporting to netCDF" checkbox. In the Advion Mass Express "Sample List" window enter the "Sample List Setup" window and activate the "Exporting to netCDF" checkbox. The data will now automatically be converted after each run and saved to the same data folder the *.datx is configured to be saved to.

Data transfer to the Chemotion ELN

The Advion express CMS' computer and Chemotion ELN needs access to a common network storage location. The network storage can be set up on a third-party storage (a NAS server, shared storage of another PC, etc.). In this case, the LSDF storage service from KIT has been used.

An EFW executable needs to be configured, downloaded from the EFW builder, and set to run on the device's PC. The EFW program will run on the device's computer in the background and transfer the *.datx data files and the converted *.cdf files from the local data storage to the network location accessible by both the device's computer and the ELN. Details can be found [here](#).

Configurations in Chemotion ELN

The Chemotion ELN's data collector has to be configured to collect the mass spectrometer's data from the network location.

As for the file collector mechanism, there are two options.

- Collecting attachment files from emails
- Collecting files or folders from local drives or over SCP

For this procedure, the file collection from local drives or over SCP needs to be chosen and configured to collect the data from the network drive to which the EFW program has uploaded it. You can find details [here](#).